

MODELLING FOR DELAMINATION DETECTION IN A LAMINATED COMPOSITE BEAM USING PIEZOELECTRIC LAYERS

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ABSTRACT:

In order to identify the presence, size and axial location of a delamination embedded in a laminated composite beam, a dynamic analytical model is proposed and then used to predict the first three order frequencies and sensor charge output (SCO) distribution along the beam length when a beam system is excited by an external force. The required sensors are made of piezoelectric layers and are bonded on the top and bottom surfaces of a laminated composite beam. Using the present model, the effects of the delamination length l_d , sensor thickness t_s , and its Young's modulus Y_s , Young's modulus for the host beam Y_b , Young's modulus for the adhesive layer Y_{ad} , as well as external force F_e on the SCO distribution and delamination detection sensitivity (DDS) are investigated. It is noted that the SCO distribution is closely related to t_s , Y_s , Y_b , l_d , F_e , and is slightly affected by Y_{ad} . For the cases of first and third order frequencies, the DDS generally increases with l_d , Y_{ad} and decreases with t_s , Y_s , Y_b . The influence of F_e on the DDS is not significant. For the second order frequency, the effects of t_s , Y_s , Y_b , Y_{ad} , l_d , F_e on the DDS is minor. A comparison between the present analytical and finite element analysis (FEA) models is conducted for the first three order frequencies. A good agreement between these two models is noted.

KEYWORDS:

Dynamic analytical model, delamination detection sensitivity (DDS), piezoelectric sensors, sensor charge output (SCO).

INTRODUCTION

Delamination is a frequently encountered mode of damage in laminated composites, which are widely used in aerospace structures. As a result of separation of adjoining plies, existence of a delamination causes reduction in composite stiffness and strength. It also results in the change in parameters like buckling load, natural frequency, etc. [1-2]. Thus, delamination detection has received considerable attention in the composite community since it is important to assess whether such internal damage has the potential for catastrophic growth. However, due to that delaminations are embedded in a laminated composite, they are usually invisible or difficult to be detected by visual inspection [3].

In the past several years, a relatively new area of non-destructive delamination monitoring emerges. It involves using piezoelectric sensors/actuators, bonded on laminated composite structure surfaces and/or embedded in composite structures during manufacturing, to detect delaminations. For example, Teboub and Hajela [2] presented a neural network based strategy for online damage (e.g., delamination) detection in unsymmetric composite laminate beams, in which a network of piezoelectric sensors/actuators have been embedded in a structure during manufacturing. Keilers and Chang [4-6] conducted an experimental and analytical investigation to detect a delamination and to estimate its size and location for laminated composite structures. The experimental test was conducted using piezoelectrics attached to a composite beam with and without an artificial delamination, and the structural analysis was developed for predicting the output voltages of the sensors when a delaminated beam was excited by the actuators. Saravanos et al [7] proposed a detection technique to identify the delamination in composite beams using piezoelectric sensors. By employing this technique, the presence and location of a delamination can be detected based on variations in

the voltage, which is generated in the piezoelectric layers when the beam is excited either externally or via piezoelectric actuators. Yin et al [8] used a modified quasi three-dimensional finite element method to detect damage such as delamination in a laminated composite through piezoelectric film sensors. However, delamination detection at the larger value of frequency was not discussed in above methods.

In this paper, a dynamic analytical method is presented to predict the presence, size and axial location of a delamination in a laminated composite beam using piezoelectric sensors. It is based on monitoring SCO distribution along the beam length for the first three order frequencies, namely frequency *I*, *II* and *III*, when the structure is excited externally. The theoretical foundation of this method is briefly outlined in the following section, and the required governing equations are presented for the case of external vibration excitation. Subsequently, a numerical study is conducted to investigate the effects of t_s , Y_s , Y_b , Y_{ad} , l_d , F_e on the SCO distribution and DDS that is defined by the change rate of the SCO around the delamination tip. For the sake of validating the present model, a comparison between the present prediction and finite element analysis (FEA) results is also conducted. However, due to the fact that investigation into the delamination detection of a beam system using piezoelectric layers is very limited, it is difficult to quantitatively compare the present results with those available in the literature.

MODEL DEVELOPMENT

In this investigation, we consider a laminated composite beam bonded with identical piezoelectric layers on both top and bottom beam surfaces (see Fig. 1). The width and length of the beam system are denoted by b and L_b . The thicknesses of beam, adhesive layers and piezoelectric layers are denoted by t_b , t_{ad} , and t_s , respectively. For the sake of simplicity, a single delamination embedded in a cantilever composite beam system with piezoelectric layers is considered here. It is assumed that the delamination occurs throughout the width of the host composite beam and the delamination front lines are straight and perpendicular to the length direction of the beam.

Figure 1 A schematic for a beam system with delamination

Due to the geometry shown in Fig. 1, the beam system can be subdivided into three major span-wise regions, namely region *I*, *II* and *III*, as shown in Fig. 1. For region *I* and *III*, they can be considered to be made of three segments (i.e., upper sensor, beam and lower sensor segment), and for the region *II*, it consists of four segments (i.e., upper sensor, upper delaminated beam, lower delaminated beam and lower sensor segment). Each segment is modelled as an Euler beam (see the free-body diagram Fig. 2(a) for the region *I* and (b) for

the region *II*). The free-body diagram for the region *III* can be obtained by replacing 1 with 3 in Fig. 2(a).

For simplicity, the contact and friction between the upper and lower delaminated beam segments are not considered here, and thus it is assumed that there is no stress transferring between these two segments. The motion for each region is described by the upper and lower sensor transverse displacements w_{kus} and w_{kls} , the beam transverse displacements w_{kb} due to bending, and the pure longitudinal displacement u_{kus} and u_{kls} for the upper and lower sensors, and u_{kb} for the beam, where $k = 1, 2, 3$ for region *I*, *II* and *III*, respectively. Hence, based on the free-body diagram shown in Fig. 2, the corresponding equations of motion for the top sensor, host beam and bottom sensor in all three regions can be obtained as follows:

(a) Free-body diagram for the region *I*

(b) Free-body diagram for the region *II*

Figure 2 Free-body diagrams for regions I and II

For the top (or upper) sensor segment

$$\rho_s A_s \ddot{u}_{kus} = \frac{\partial T_{kus}}{\partial x} + \tau_{ku} b, \quad \rho_s A_s \ddot{w}_{kus} = \frac{\partial Q_{kus}}{\partial x} + \sigma_{ku} b, \quad \frac{\partial M_{kus}}{\partial x} - Q_{kus} + \frac{\tau_{ku} b t_s}{2} = 0 \quad (1-3)$$

For the bottom (or lower) sensor segment

$$\rho_s A_s \ddot{u}_{kls} = \frac{\partial T_{kls}}{\partial x} - \tau_{kl} b, \quad \rho_s A_s \ddot{w}_{kls} = \frac{\partial Q_{kls}}{\partial x} - \sigma_{kl} b, \quad \frac{\partial M_{kls}}{\partial x} - Q_{kls} + \frac{\tau_{kl} b t_s}{2} = 0 \quad (4-6)$$

For the host beam segment without delamination

$$\rho_b A_b \ddot{u}_{kb} = \frac{\partial T_{kb}}{\partial x} + (\tau_{kl} - \tau_{ku}) b, \quad \rho_b A_b \ddot{w}_{kb} = \frac{\partial Q_{kb}}{\partial x} + (\sigma_{kl} - \sigma_{ku}) b, \quad \frac{\partial M_{kb}}{\partial x} - Q_{kb} + \frac{(\tau_{kl} + \tau_{ku}) b t_b}{2} = 0 \quad (7-9)$$

For the upper delaminated beam segment in the region *II*,

$$\rho_b A_{2ub} \ddot{u}_{2ub} = \frac{\partial T_{2ub}}{\partial x} - \tau_{2u} b, \quad \rho_b A_{2ub} \ddot{w}_{2ub} = \frac{\partial Q_{2ub}}{\partial x} - \sigma_{2u} b, \quad \frac{\partial M_{2ub}}{\partial x} - Q_{2ub} + \frac{\tau_{2u} b t_{ub}}{2} = 0 \quad (10-12)$$

For the lower delaminated beam segment in the region *II*,

$$\rho_b A_{2lb} \ddot{u}_{2lb} = \frac{\partial T_{2lb}}{\partial x} + \tau_{2l} b, \quad \rho_b A_{2lb} \ddot{w}_{2lb} = \frac{\partial Q_{2lb}}{\partial x} + \sigma_{2l} b, \quad \frac{\partial M_{2lb}}{\partial x} - Q_{2lb} + \frac{\tau_{2l} b t_{lb}}{2} = 0 \quad (13-15)$$

Due to $\varepsilon_x = \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} - z \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2}$ and $\sigma_x = Y \varepsilon_x$, where Y is the Young's modulus, the axial forces and bending moments for the host beam, top and bottom sensors in all three regions are given by

$$T_i = \bar{A}_i \frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x}, \quad M_i = \bar{D}_i \frac{\partial^2 w_i}{\partial x^2}, \quad (16-17)$$

$$i = \begin{cases} kus & \text{for the top sensor segment in region } k (k = 1, 2, 3), \\ kls & \text{for the bottom sensor segment in region } k (k = 1, 2, 3), \\ kb & \text{for the host beam segment in region } k (k = 1, 3), \\ 2ub, 2lb & \text{for the upper and lower delaminated beam segments in region } II. \end{cases}$$

$$\bar{A}_i = \begin{cases} bY_s t_s & \text{for the top and bottom sensor segments in all three regions,} \\ bY_b t_b & \text{for the host beam segments in region } I \text{ and } III, \\ bY_b t_{ub}, bY_b t_{lb} & \text{for the upper and lower delaminated beam segments in region } II, \end{cases}$$

$$\bar{D}_i = \begin{cases} -\frac{bY_s t_s^3}{12} & \text{for the top and bottom sensor segments in all three regions,} \\ -\frac{bY_b t_b^3}{12} & \text{for the host beam segments in region } I \text{ and } III, \\ -\frac{bY_b t_{ub}^3}{12}, -\frac{bY_b t_{lb}^3}{12} & \text{for the upper and lower delaminated beam segments in region } II, \end{cases}$$

Under the constant shear and peel strain assumption [9], the shear and peel stress between the sensor and host beam can be obtained using the following equations

$$\tau = G_{ad} \gamma_{1u}, \quad \sigma_{1u} = \frac{Y_{ad}(1-\nu_{ad})}{(1-2\nu_{ad})(1+\nu_{ad})t_{ad}} (w_b - w_t),$$

$$\gamma_{1u} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial w_t}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial w_b}{\partial x} \right) + \frac{1}{2t_{ad}} \left(t_t \frac{\partial w_t}{\partial x} + t_b \frac{\partial w_b}{\partial x} \right) + \frac{u_b - u_t}{t_{ad}}, \quad (18-20)$$

where subscripts t and b stand for top and bottom layer, respectively.

For a cantilever beam system, a total of eighteen applicable boundary conditions can be obtained and listed as follows:

Fixed end:

$$T_{1us} = 0, \quad Q_{1us} = 0, \quad M_{1us} = 0, \quad u_{1b} = 0, \quad w_{1b} = 0, \quad \frac{\partial w_{1b}}{\partial x} = 0, \quad T_{1ls} = 0, \quad Q_{1ls} = 0, \quad M_{1ls} = 0, \quad (21)$$

Free end:

$$T_{3us} = 0, \quad Q_{3us} = 0, \quad M_{3us} = 0, \quad T_{3b} = 0, \quad Q_{3b} = 0, \quad M_{3b} = 0, \quad T_{3ls} = 0, \quad Q_{3ls} = 0, \quad M_{3ls} = 0, \quad (22)$$

For the case considered here, a total of forty-two continuity conditions exist at the interface between region I and II as well as that between region II and III in order to ensure the displacements and forces to be identical at the interfaces. These continuity conditions are given below,

At the interface between region I and II :

$$u_{1us} = u_{2us}, \quad w_{1us} = w_{2us}, \quad \frac{\partial w_{1us}}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial w_{2us}}{\partial x}, \quad T_{1us} = T_{2us}, \quad Q_{1us} = Q_{2us}, \quad M_{1us} = M_{2us},$$

$$u_{1b} + \frac{t_b - t_{ub}}{2} \frac{\partial w_{1b}}{\partial x} = u_{2ub}, \quad u_{1b} - \frac{t_b - t_{lb}}{2} \frac{\partial w_{1b}}{\partial x} = u_{2lb}, \quad w_{1b} = w_{2ub}, \quad w_{1b} = w_{2lb}, \quad \frac{\partial w_{1b}}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial w_{2ub}}{\partial x},$$

$$\frac{\partial w_{1b}}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial w_{2lb}}{\partial x}, \quad T_{1b} = T_{2ub} + T_{2lb}, \quad Q_{1b} = Q_{2ub} + Q_{2lb}, \quad M_{1b} = M_{2ub} + M_{2lb} + \frac{t_b - t_{lb}}{2} T_{2lb} - \frac{t_b - t_{ub}}{2} T_{2ub},$$

$$u_{1ls} = u_{2ls}, \quad w_{1ls} = w_{2ls}, \quad \frac{\partial w_{1ls}}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial w_{2ls}}{\partial x}, \quad T_{1ls} = T_{2ls}, \quad Q_{1ls} = Q_{2ls}, \quad M_{1ls} = M_{2ls}. \quad (23)$$

At the interface between region II and III :

$$u_{2us} = u_{3us}, \quad w_{2us} = w_{3us}, \quad \frac{\partial w_{2us}}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial w_{3us}}{\partial x}, \quad T_{2us} = T_{3us}, \quad Q_{2us} = Q_{3us}, \quad M_{2us} = M_{3us},$$

$$u_{2ub} = u_{3b} + \frac{t_b - t_{ub}}{2} \frac{\partial w_{2ub}}{\partial x}, \quad u_{2lb} = u_{3b} - \frac{t_b - t_{lb}}{2} \frac{\partial w_{2lb}}{\partial x}, \quad w_{2ub} = w_{3b}, \quad w_{2lb} = w_{3b}, \quad \frac{\partial w_{2ub}}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial w_{3b}}{\partial x},$$

$$\frac{\partial w_{2lb}}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial w_{3b}}{\partial x}, \quad T_{2ub} + T_{2lb} = T_{3b}, \quad Q_{2ub} + Q_{2lb} = Q_{3b}, \quad M_{2ub} + M_{2lb} + \frac{t_b - t_{lb}}{2} T_{2lb} - \frac{t_b - t_{ub}}{2} T_{2ub} = M_{3b},$$

$$u_{2ls} = u_{3ls}, w_{2ls} = w_{3ls}, \frac{\partial w_{2ls}}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial w_{3ls}}{\partial x}, T_{2ls} = T_{3ls}, Q_{2ls} = Q_{3ls}, M_{2ls} = M_{3ls}. \quad (24)$$

By numerically solving the governing equations (1-20) together with their boundary and continuity conditions (21-24), the required natural frequencies and absolute value of the strain distribution $|\varepsilon_s(x, \omega)|$ along the top and bottom sensor surfaces can be obtained, and thus for a selected natural frequency ω , the sensor charge output for the top or bottom piezoelectric layer can be obtained by

$$Q(\omega) = b \int_0^{L_b} e_{31s} |\varepsilon_s(x, \omega)| dx \quad (25)$$

where e_{31s} is the piezoelectric constant for a piezoelectric layer.

It is worth mentioning that for the sake of obtaining the SCO distribution along the beam length, region *I*, *II* and *III* are further divided into N_1, N_2, N_3 finite elements. Following the similar procedure mentioned above, the required equations of motion and continuity conditions for each element can be obtained. Thus, the solution for the beam system as a whole is obtained in terms of the solutions of all elements using the classical beam theory, appropriate boundary and continuity conditions. In addition, it is known that the SCO can only be measured through the electrodes on the piezoelectric sensor [8]. In order to obtain a continuous curve of the SCO along the beam length, a number of electrode strips are required and evenly distributed along the beam length. Hence, for a selected natural frequency ω , the SCO measured from an electrode strip, which is bounded on a piezoelectric layer element with the length of Δx and located at $x = x_a$, is given by

$$q(x_a, \omega) = b \int_{x_a - \frac{\Delta x}{2}}^{x_a + \frac{\Delta x}{2}} e_{31s} |\varepsilon_s(\xi, \omega)| d\xi, \quad \text{where } \frac{\Delta x}{2} \leq x_a \leq L_b - \frac{\Delta x}{2} \quad (26)$$

Using equation (26), the SCO distribution for various locations of the delamination, delamination lengths and gaps can be predicted. It is worth pointing out that in practice, accurate detection of a delamination using electrode strips, which are evenly distributed in the x direction, may be limited by the number and size of electrode strips.

NUMERICAL STUDY

In this investigation, a cantilever beam system with beam length $L_b=0.3\text{m}$, beam width $b=0.02\text{m}$ and host beam thickness $t_b=1.9\text{mm}$ is considered, in which a delamination with delamination length $l_d=0.05\text{m}$ is located at mid-plane and mid-length $X_d=0.15\text{m}$, where X_d is the distance of the delamination centre from the fixed end. The sensor thickness t_s is selected to be 0.4mm and that of adhesive layer t_{ad} is chosen to be 0.15mm . The beam and sensor are made of T300/GY260 plain weave composite and piezoelectric layers, respectively. The required complex Young's modulus for the host beam, piezoelectric sensors and adhesive layers are equal to $65.68(1+0.011i)\text{GPa}$, $69.2(1+0.011i)\text{GPa}$ and $2.15(1+0.011i)\text{GPa}$, respectively. The piezoelectric constant e_{31s} for a sensor is chosen to be 44.37C/m^2 . The density for the host beam, sensors and adhesive layers are selected to be 1527.38kg/m^3 , 7600kg/m^3 and 1600kg/m^3 , respectively [10-12]. For the sake of investigating the effects of $t_s, Y_s, Y_{ad}, Y_b, l_d$, and F_e on the SCO and DDS, the required values of parameters are chosen to be 0.05m and 0.1m for l_d , 0.4mm and 0.7mm for t_s , $34.6(1+0.011i)\text{GPa}$ and $69.2(1+0.011i)\text{GPa}$ for Y_s , $1.075(1+0.011i)\text{GPa}$ and $2.15(1+0.011i)\text{GPa}$ for Y_{ad} , $32.84(1+0.011i)\text{GPa}$ and $65.68(1+0.011i)\text{GPa}$ for Y_b , as well as 10N and 20N for F_e , respectively.

For the host beam with and without delamination, where the delamination with $l_d=0.05\text{m}$ is located at $X_d=0.15\text{m}$, the corresponding variation trends of the SCO obtained from the top (or bottom) sensor surface along the beam length can be obtained using the present analytical model, and are plotted in Fig. 3(a)-(c) for the first three order frequencies. It is noted from Fig. 3 that the abrupt axial discontinuities in the SCO distribution clearly indicate the tips of a delamination, and thus the presence, size and axial location of a delamination are clearly outlined, especially for the case of frequency III.

The effects of l_d , t_s , Y_s , Y_{ad} , Y_b and F_e on the SCO distributions along the beam length for the first three order frequencies are illustrated in Figs. 4-9, respectively. From these figures, it is noted that the SCO distributions are sensitive to the change of l_d , t_s , Y_s , Y_b , F_e , but the influence of Y_{ad} on the SCO is minor. These figures also reveal that for the cases with large value of l_d , F_e and small value of t_s , Y_s , Y_b , the SCO distribution is more sensitive to a delamination than those with small value of l_d , F_e and larger value of t_s , Y_s , Y_b .

Figure 3 The predicted SCO distribution for the beams with and without delamination

Figure 4 Comparison of SCO distributions between $l_d=0.05\text{m}$ and $l_d=0.1\text{m}$ for the first three order frequencies

Figure 5 Comparison of SCO distributions between $t_s=0.4\text{mm}$ and $t_s=0.7\text{mm}$ for the first three order frequencies

(a) Frequency *I* (b) Frequency *II* (c) Frequency *III*
 Figure 6 Comparison of SCO distributions between $Y_s=69.2(1+0.011i)$ GPa and $Y_s=34.6(1+0.011i)$ GPa for the first three order frequencies

(a) Frequency *I* (b) Frequency *II* (c) Frequency *III*
 Figure 7 Comparison of SCO distributions between $Y_{ad}=2.15(1+0.011i)$ GPa and $Y_{ad}=1.075(1+0.011i)$ GPa for the first three order frequencies

(a) Frequency *I* (b) Frequency *II* (c) Frequency *III*
 Figure 8 Comparison of SCO distributions between $Y_b=65.68(1+0.011i)$ and $Y_b=32.84(1+0.011i)$ for the first three order frequencies

(a) Frequency *I* (b) Frequency *II* (c) Frequency *III*
 Figure 9 Comparison of SCO distributions between $F_e=10$ N and $F_e=20$ N for the first three order frequencies

(a) For the case of frequency I (b) For the case of frequency III
 Figure 10 Diagrams used to illustrate the calculation for the DDSs at the delamination tips

It is worth pointing out that since the DDS for the case of frequency *II* is not sensitive to the change of l_d , t_s , Y_s , Y_{ad} , Y_b and F_e , the values of DDS listed in Table 1 is only for the cases of frequency *I* and *III*, in which the baseline case is referred to as a beam system with $X_d=0.15\text{m}$, $l_d=0.05\text{m}$, $t_s=0.4\text{mm}$, $Y_s=69.2(1+0.011i)\text{GPa}$, $Y_{ad}=2.15(1+0.011i)\text{GPa}$, $Y_b=65.68(1+0.011i)\text{GPa}$ and $F_e=10\text{N}$, and the value of DDS is obtained by

$$DDS = \frac{\text{The absolute value of SCO discrepancy at the right (or left) delamination tip}}{\text{The value of SCO just ahead of (or behind) the right (or left) delamination tip}} \times 100\% \quad (27)$$

For example, for the cases shown in Fig.10(a)-(b), the DDS at the right (or left) tip is given by

$$DDS = \frac{|\text{The SCO value at the point a} - \text{The SCO value at the point b}|}{\text{The SCO value at the point b}} \times 100\% \quad (28)$$

Table 1 A comparison of the DDSs for various cases

DDS (%)	Right tip		Left tip	
	Freq. <i>I</i>	Freq. <i>III</i>	Freq. <i>I</i>	Freq. <i>III</i>
Baseline	6.6	34.5	13.2	29
$l_d=0.1\text{m}$	15.1	61.8	54.7	42.1
$t_s=0.7\text{mm}$	3.7	15.5	7.5	16.1
$Y_s=34.6(1+0.011i)\text{GPa}$	6.6	47	18.6	41
$Y_{ad}=1.075(1+0.011i)\text{GPa}$	4.8	27.6	9.9	22.8
$Y_b=32.84(1+0.011i)\text{GPa}$	6	47	11.6	41
$F_e=20\text{N}$	6.6	34.5	13.2	29

In Table 1, the 2nd row lists the DDS values for the baseline case, while the 3rd to the 8th row tabulate the DDS values for the cases in which only one parameter is varied as listed in the 1st column. An inspection of the results in the 3rd to 8th rows reveals that F_e does not affect the value of DDS, whereas all other parameters have an influence on DDS value, especially for the case of third order frequency (i.e., Freq. *III* in Table 1). Table 1 also reveals that for the right or left delamination tip, its corresponding DDS value increases with l_d , Y_{ad} and decreases with t_s , Y_s . It is interesting that an increase in Y_b results in a slight increase in the DDS value for the case of frequency *I* and a significant decrease in the DDS value for the case of frequency *III*.

VALIDATION OF THE PRESENT MODEL

A total number of eleven 2D plane strain FEA models are developed to validate the present analytical model. These FEA models are established using the FEA software Strand7 [13-14]. A comparison of the first three order frequencies between the present analytical and

FEA models is conducted. However, due to lack of the required data, a quantitative comparison between the present results with those available in the literature is difficult.

For the first six models (i.e., case *a* to *f*), a delamination with $R_g=0.0625$ (where $R_g=t_g/t_b$, t_g is the delamination gap shown in Fig. 1) and $R_x(=X_d/L_b)=0.5$ is located in mid-plane. The delamination length for the cases of *a* to *f* is chosen to be 0.03, 0.06, 0.09, 0.12, 0.15 and 0.18m, respectively. For the last five models (i.e., case *A* to *E*), a delamination with $R_g=0.0625$ and $R_l(=l_d/L_b)=0.2$ is located at $X_d=0.045, 0.09, 0.15, 0.18$ and 0.24 m from the fixed end, respectively. Each FEA model is established using about 15000 four-node plate elements. The first three order frequencies predicted using the FEA model and present analytical model are obtained and listed in Table 2 for the first six cases and Table 3 for the last five cases.

From Table 2 and 3, it is noted that there is a very good agreement between these two models. For the first six cases, the difference between two models ranges from 5.5% to 7.8% for the first order frequency, 5.4% to 7.9% for the second order frequency, and 5.7% to 10.7% for the third order frequency. In addition, Table 2 reveals that with the increase in the delamination length, the frequencies obtained using the FEA model decrease. This is consistent with that predicted using the present analytical model. For the last five cases, the difference between two models ranges from 4.9% to 5.9% for the first order frequency, 3.8% to 7.2% for the second order frequency and 5.1% to 7.5% for the third order frequency, respectively. It is also noted from Table 3 that the variation trends of the frequency with X_d gained using the present analytical model corresponds well to those obtained using the FEA model.

Table 2 Comparison of the first three order frequencies between the FEA and analytical results for various delamination lengths

Case	FEA model			Present analytical model		
	Freq.I	Freq.II	Freq.III	Freq.I	Freq.II	Freq.III
	(Hz)					
a	22.78	143.00	393.90	21.53	135.30	371.27
b	22.68	142.96	362.07	21.42	134.94	335.04
c	22.40	142.30	314.68	21.13	134.58	284.69
d	21.97	140.00	276.91	20.59	131.89	247.73
e	21.27	135.00	255.00	19.80	126.05	227.64
f	20.37	126.89	203.08	18.79	116.90	219.36

Table 3 Comparison of the first three order frequencies between the FEA and analytical results for various axial delamination locations

Case	FEA model			Analytical model		
	Freq.I	Freq.II	Freq.III	Freq.I	Freq.II	Freq.III
	(Hz)					
A	22.68	133.03	359.67	21.34	123.46	332.99
B	22.45	137.66	397.30	21.36	128.90	377.02
C	22.68	142.96	362.07	21.42	134.94	335.04
D	22.72	142.39	377.37	21.47	135.33	351.82
E	22.81	140.00	387.40	21.59	134.65	363.97

CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, an analytical model is proposed to identify the presence, size and axial location of a delamination embedded in a cantilever laminated composite beam. A parametric study is presented for investigation into the effects of l_d , t_s , Y_s , Y_{ad} , Y_b and F_e on the SCO distribution and DDS. It is revealed from the parametric study that for the first three order frequencies, the SCO distribution along the beam length is closely related to the values of l_d , F_e , t_s , Y_s , Y_b . The influence of Y_{ad} on the SCO distribution is minor. The DDS generally

increases with l_d , Y_{ad} and decreases with t_s , Y_s . An increase in Y_b results in slight increase in the DDS for the case of frequency I and a significant decrease in the DDS for the case of frequency III . The influence of F_e on the DDS is not significant. Hence, for the purpose of identifying a delamination effectively, it is suggested to select the sensors with small value of t_s and Y_s and the adhesive with larger value of Y_{ad} . A comparison between the present analytical and FEA models reveals that a good agreement exists between these two models.

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